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Tragic Legacy Of Violence Against Women In Armed Conflict: A History Of Silence

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This study delves into the profound violence inflicted upon women in armed conflict, tracing its roots in societal discrimination and oppression during peacetime. It emphasizes the often-overlooked contributions of women in conflict zones, urging the integration of women's rights into legal frameworks and systematic support from international agencies.

Recognizing women's roles in peace-building is deemed crucial for sustainable peace. The study exposes harrowing realities, detailing atrocities like puncturing wombs with guns. It highlights women's active engagement in conflict dynamics and the interplay between HIV/AIDS and armed conflict, emphasizing the need for comprehensive support and international collaboration.

Addressing the conundrum against violence, the article proposes targeted sanctions, truth commissions, and integrating gender perspectives into peace operations. It calls for a holistic humanitarian effort addressing women's specific challenges during conflicts. The study reveals the normalization of violence against women as conflicts escalate, focusing on the intersection with human trafficking and advocating for targeted interventions.

Confronting domestic violence, the study proposes international commissions and targeted sanctions against trafficking, urging comprehensive support for survivors. The impact on women's health, especially reproductive health challenges, is examined, emphasizing the need for a holistic approach to dismantle systemic barriers. The study urges a critical reevaluation of societal responses to violence against women in armed conflicts, prompting concerted efforts for positive change.

Introduction

The profound and disturbing violence inflicted upon women during times of conflict is not an isolated phenomenon stemming solely from the conditions of war; rather, it is intricately connected to the pervasive violence embedded in the fabric of women's lives during peacetime. [1]Globally, women grapple with violence simply because of their gender, navigating a landscape where their rights and autonomy are often subjugated beneath the weight of discrimination and oppression.

✓ The spectra of gender based persecution looms large, casting a dark shadow that encompasses sexual

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